

Journey Into the Teaching Profession: Views of Newly Hired Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Teachers

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Abstract. This study analyzed the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational insights drawn from the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the actual teaching profession. A qualitative approach to phenomenological research from 8 newly hired TLE teachers from the different schools in cluster 1 on their experiences as they embark into the actual teaching profession was observed: experienced reality shock, overwhelming experiences, experience teaching through workshops, and experience teaching practical knowledge. While the newly hired TLE teachers coping mechanisms for success were as follows: attending mentoring and coaching, managing time well, and being adaptable. Through their experiences and coping mechanisms, we generated new knowledge and ideas on their challenges as they embarked on the teaching profession. Finally, the educational management insights drawn from the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers were the following: adjusting to the school setting, building a professional learning group, going with positive workmates, and observing other teachers. These themes can be described as an input in successfully crafting and conducting training for newly hired TLE teachers to capacitate them on the different strategies and techniques as they embark into the teaching profession. The newly hired teachers may continue to contact their colleagues from other schools for possible benchmarking. Despite the limited technology resources available to capacitate the newly hired teachers, they may keep encouraging all possible partners for potential partnerships.

KEY WORDS

1. newly hired TLE teachers
2. coping mechanisms
3. educational management insights

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1. Introduction

Technology and livelihood education is a field that focuses on providing students with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed in specific occupations and careers. In the case of newly hired technology and livelihood education teachers, it is expected that challenges and difficulties will arise as they are new to the service and have little experience in handling this subject. They will need time and effort to address the learner's needs. Since the creation of this course or subject, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is to provide students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for gainful employment and entrepreneurial opportunities in agriculture, home economics, industrial arts, and information and communication technology. Learning about teaching during initial teacher education differs from learning about teaching while teaching (Larkin et al., 2016). A further distinction can

be made between learning to teach and becoming a teacher (Alnahdi, 2014). The first year of teaching is the most challenging part for all newly hired teachers. After leaving the role of being undergraduate students and taking on the role of teachers, they soon become overwhelmed with the responsibilities of the curriculum, diverse student behaviors, student motivation (Salandanan, 2016), classroom management (Agno, 2009; Basturk Tastepe, 2015), student learning assessment (Agu et al., 2013) and feeling the lack of support from others. These mixed experiences, such as challenges and frustrations, are aspects of beginning teachers. As practicing professional newly hired teachers, we all go through life cycles, and each person has his/her ways of dealing with their emotional changes. Anent to this, the greatest struggles of a professional teacher as an individual are not fought on battlefields; they are fought not only inside the classroom but in human hearts as they struggle with fear, frustration, stress, a lack of self-confidence, feelings of inadequacy, inferiority, and the inability to cope with circumstances not to their liking. While these challenges can defeat everyone, they can also serve as catalysts for improvement in preparation for favorable development in the cognitive, spiritual, social, and personal, as well as in understanding one's own professional opportunities and challenges (Bilbao, 2012). Newly-hired technology and livelihood education teachers are faced with many experiences. They are beset with a multitude of concerns and anxieties. Such feelings are expected but should not be the deterrent to their desire to "learn to teach" (Salandanan, 2005). Newly-hired secondary teachers in Hongkong experienced problems related to teaching and lesson preparation, including dealing with individual differences (Chong, 2011). Lesson plan making, administrators having hard attitude, student's negative attitudes, overwork, over-expecting co-teachers, and anxiety due to difficulties encountered with teaching, paperwork, and other school activities are the common struggles of new teachers in the Philippines (Llego, 2017). It is important to provide TLE teachers with experiences in teaching practices in order to teach 'teaching basic competencies and to make theoretical knowledge more meaningful. In this context, preparing TLE teachers to be successful in their first year of teaching should be the main goal of teacher training Beck et al., (2007). No matter how well-trained individuals graduate from the teacher training programs, they face real-life problems after beginning their teaching careers. Unless the teacher is confronted with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors they will need in real educational environments and gain experience, the theoretical knowledge they receive will not mean much for them (Saritaş, 2007). The first years of the teaching profession are an important stage in which teachers encounter difficulties and problems the most and try to cope with these problems (Casey, 2005; Ingvarson et al., 2007; Feiman-Nemser, 2003). Denscombe (1985) stated that the first year of teaching is key for the years to come. Transition to the teaching profession can be challenging for newcomers (Eaton Sisson, 2008). Some refer to the experiences of teachers who are left on their own in their classrooms for the first time in the early years of their profession as being lost at sea (Kauffman et al., 2002; Johnson Birkeland, 2003). None of the teachers who just started the profession encountered situations that exactly match the expectations of their first year or do not know exactly how to cope with the difficulties they have experienced (Wyatt III White, 2007). A successful start is critical to both the teachers' careers and the education of the students. Positive experiences in the early years help teachers to build solid perspectives and approaches for the rest of their careers. In connection the newly hired teachers perform a significant job in the academic journey of the students. Newly hired

teachers must apply suitable practices to meet student needs. The implementation of correct teaching practices plays a vital role in the classroom, and it influences the performance of the students. Therefore, the instructional practices used should be fitted to the kind of students in the classroom; if not, these may need to change (Knapp, 2013). Moreover, newly hired teachers can practice professional opportunities and challenges, including the principles and guidelines that will assist students in finding peace, confidence, and fulfillment, not feeling defeated by fear, frustration, stress, or hopelessness- but being an overcomer. As declared by Zamorski Haydyn (2012), not everyone grows up to have an innate sense of high self-esteem or worthiness. Everybody has those rough nights and days, negative moods, or tiredness. Thus, to become an effective teacher, everyone has their own stories. Stories along one's journey of practicing the profession toward success, as Cruickshank et al. (2010) pointed out, newly hired teachers should be equipped with knowledge, values, and skills about teaching strategies. The Philippine education system was fully implementing an essential educational reform, that is, the K to 12 curricula in primary education, which resulted in unending educational, social, and political issues. Consequently, the Department of Education has continuously hired thousands of teachers for the past years. For example, roughly 61,000 in 2013 (Salaveria, 2012) and some 39,000 for the school year 2015-16 (Malipot, 2014) eventually caused an exodus of teachers, including those from higher education

institutions, because of the fear of being displaced in higher education once the senior high school commences. Most of these newly hired teachers are seasoned or experienced teachers in private schools who have decided to transfer to government schools due to low pay, poor work benefits, and no security of tenure (Sambalod, 2014). In the local scenario, particularly in the Holy Cross of Agdao, Davao City, and nearby schools, newly hired technology and livelihood education teachers encountered various experiences as they embarked on the teaching profession. Some experiences are positive, while others negatively affect the teaching profession, which might lead to quitting the service. In this context, this study was conceptualized to collect the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as it would serve as a benchmark for incoming educators.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to find out the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the teaching profession, their coping mechanisms, and insights into the informants' experiences. The results would, therefore, serve as reference material for future researchers in this area and shed more light on how newly hired TLE teachers adjust in the actual teaching profession.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intends to get insights and experiences from newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the teaching profession. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark into the actual teaching profession?
- (2) How did the newly hired TLE teachers cope with the challenges encountered as they embarked on the actual teaching profession?
- (3) What educational insights are drawn from the experiences of the informants?

1.3. Significance of the Study—To determine the outcomes of this study and to whom

the findings were addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. De-

partment of Education Officials. The study's findings would encourage the DepEd officials, particularly in Holy Cross of Agdao and the nearby schools in the Davao City division, to be more flexible in terms of teaching, especially the newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the actual teaching profession. Newly Hired Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers. The study would be significant to them since they would be able to know the issues and insights on their experiences as they embark on the actual teaching profession. Stakeholders. This study would be significant to them since it would give them insights into how to assist school administrators in developing newly hired TLE teachers professionally. Their role was vital since they are part of the School-Based Management System for curriculum development. Future Researchers. The findings provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

1.4. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Technology and Livelihood Education- One of the learning areas of the Secondary Education Curriculum used in Philippine secondary schools. As a subject in high school, its component areas are Home Economics, Agri-Fishery Arts, Industrial Arts, and Information and Communication Technology. Newly Hired TLE Teacher. Secondary school teachers for not more than three years, teaching students from grades seven through twelve, specializing in Technology and Livelihood Education.

1.5. Review of Significant Literature—This section reviews key literature on performance-based assessments in distance learning and the experiences of newly hired Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers.

1.5.1. Experiences of Newly Hired TLE Teachers—New teachers often face "reality shock," where classroom realities differ from

expectations, leading to feelings of alienation and insufficient support (Jensen et al., 2008; Veenman, 1984). These challenges include managing classroom discipline, navigating school systems, and handling personal and professional isolation (Chubbuck et al., 2001; Richards et al., 2013). The transition to online teaching during the pandemic added further complications, with new teachers struggling to adapt to home learning environments (Canonizado, 2020).

1.5.2. Teaching Through Workshops—Workshop teaching in TLE plays a critical role in preparing students for employment by developing practical skills and self-efficacy (Lucas et al., 2009; Canter, 2000). Practical knowledge in TLE integrates theoretical content with real-life applications, promoting cognitive challenges and problem-solving skills in home economics (Granberg et al., 2017; Rendahl, 2018).

1.5.3. Mechanisms for Success of Newly Hired TLE Teachers—Teacher learning is a continuous process shaped by existing beliefs and experiences, with mentoring and coaching playing key roles in professional development (Uhlenbeck et al., 2002; Stanulis et al., 2002). Mentoring programs help bridge the gap between pre-service training and real-world classroom experiences, enabling new teachers to adapt to their roles (Jarvis Algozzine, 2006; Gold, 1996).

1.5.4. Time Management and Adaptability—Effective time management and adaptability are crucial for newly hired teachers. Managing time well enhances confidence and productivity, helping teachers balance classroom duties and personal life (Raines, 2011; Fleming, 2011). Adaptable teachers are better able to adjust their actions and emotions in response to challenging situations, leading to positive outcomes for both teachers and students (Collie Martin, 2017).

1.5.5. Educational Insights Learned from Newly Hired TLE Teachers—New teachers often face challenges adjusting to school settings due to a lack of information about organizational

practices and classroom management. Building professional learning communities and engaging with supportive colleagues are essential for overcoming these difficulties (Menon, 2011; Whitaker, 2003). Observing experienced teachers also provides new teachers with valuable insights and enhances self-awareness and professional growth (Gore, 2013).

1.6. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the Stages of Concern Theory by Fuller and Bown (1975). A closer look at the progression of teacher development for beginning teachers gives solid insight and further explanation of the real shock experienced by many new teachers in their first years of teaching. Fuller and Bown (1975) adapted Fuller's (1969) work on the stages of concern theory, which summarized the developmental patterns of concern that pre-service and beginning teachers move through in their careers and has been widely cited when examining teacher development (Conway Clark, 2003). According to this theory, teachers begin their career focused on concerns about themselves, such as personal success, and only later in their career do they progress to concerns for student learning (Burns Danyluk, 2017). The concerns theory proposes three developmental stages: concern for self, concern for teaching tasks, and impact stage. Fuller and Bown found that teachers with little teaching experience were primarily concerned about self. Examples include feelings of self-adequacy, acceptance by colleagues, concerns for good evaluations, and their desire to be successful in the classroom (Fuller Bown, 1975; Mok, 2005; Smith, 2000; Watzke, 2007). According to Fuller and Bown's theory, after teachers move through the concern for self stage, their focus is turned toward concern about teaching tasks. This second stage describes teachers' concerns about the tasks involved with teaching (Fuller Bown, 1975; Watzke, 2007). Use of instructional methods, delivery of curriculum, obstacles to effective teaching, manage-

ment of time, and access to adequate instructional materials concern teachers at this second stage (Mok, 2005; Watzke, 2007). In the final stage, Fuller and Bown found that teachers who had resolved their concerns about themselves and their tasks were then only able to become concerned about their impact on their students (Smith, 2000). In this impact stage, teachers were concerned about their students' social and learning needs. Teachers wondered if they could meet their students' diverse needs and whether their students were getting the preparation they needed to be useful members of society after graduation (Mok, 2005; Smith, 2000; Watzke, 2007). Another theory used in this study was Contemporary Cognitive Learning. Advances in cognitive psychology theory forced teachers to acknowledge how complex learning is and how diverse the means needed to assess learning fully and fairly (Resnick, 1987). According to early theories of learning based on behaviorism, complex higher-order skills are acquired bit-by-bit by breaking learning down into a series of prerequisite skills, called a building-blocks-of-knowledge approach. It was assumed that after basic skills had been learned by rote memorization, they could be assembled into complex understandings. However, research on contemporary cognitive thinking reveals that mental processes related to thinking are not restricted to a higher-order stage of mental development (Resnick Resnick, 1992; Shepard, 2000). Instead, higher-order thinking, such as reasoning, is intimately involved in learning school subjects. In other words, learning involves important components of inference, judgment, and active mental construction. For example, research on memorizing shows that even in "learning the facts," mental elaboration and judgment are required for success (Brown, 1978). Students cannot effectively memorize the facts without organizing knowledge. Shepard (2000) summarized the new findings from constructivist learning theories. First, intellectual abilities are socially

and culturally developed. Cognitive abilities are developed as parents or other significant adults interpret and guide children's interactions. Second, learners construct knowledge and understanding within a social context. Third, new learning is shaped by prior knowledge and cultural perspectives. Students with prior knowledge can reason more profoundly, elaborate as they study, and, therefore, learn more effectively in that domain. Fourth, learning involves "metacognition," or self-monitoring of learning and thinking. Expert learners can control their learning using a variety of self-monitoring strategies. Fifth, deep understanding supports transfer. Finally, cognitive performance depends on dispositions and personal identity. In other words, practical skills and motivation are as essential as knowledge in learning. Evidence from contemporary cognitive psychology (Perkins, 1992; Perkins Blythe, 1994) indicates that meaningful learning is reflective, constructive, and self-regulated. In other words, learning involves the learner's active construction of knowledge structures. To know something is not just to receive information but to interpret it and relate it to other prior knowledge that the learner already has. Thus, the presence or absence of 6 discrete bits of knowledge – the main focus of traditional multiple-choice tests – is not essential in assessing meaningful learning. Instead, how and whether students organize, structure, and use that information in context to solve complex problems, which is the main characteristic of performance assessments, is more important. Since it is a performance assessment that focuses on how students organize and apply knowledge (Khattri et al., 1998) in assessing students learning, performance assessments implement the approach suggested by contemporary learning theory. In other words, new findings from contemporary cognitive learning theory intensified interest in performance assessments. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) Experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the actual teaching profession; (2) TLE teachers coping mechanisms in addressing challenges encountered as they embark on the teaching profession; and (3) Educational insights drawn from the experiences of the informants. The use of technology has enabled the learner to have access to educational resources. Additionally, students and teachers have access to resources on the Internet that they can both use for personal or academic development. It has also made the teaching and learning process easy and enjoyable.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the study

Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group’s cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?” the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the BE Coordinators as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested the information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, “ultimates’

or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the actual teaching profession are discussed by the participants, and their strategies for addressing the challenges and educational insights are examined. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through ex-

tensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." The intention of this study was to gather information from the participants or the newly hired TLE teachers in Holy Cross of Agdao and in the nearby schools as to how they navigate the early stages in their teaching profession. It is assumed that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and mechanisms used as they embarked on the actual teaching profession. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argued that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of

information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the study context, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the teaching profession.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of newly hired teachers as they embark on the actual teaching profession in Holy Cross of Agdao and in Cluster 1, Davao City, were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well as their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark into the teaching profession became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." Using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark into the teaching profession in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research

was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the experiences and mechanisms used by the newly hired TLE teachers were explored and insights drawn as the basis for the possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focusing on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts

to extract the purest, untainted data, and some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were also helpful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as investigating their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews are useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience, both the textual description of what was experienced and

the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations would be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study is to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of the seasoned teachers, the researcher intends to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were Eight (8) newly hired TLE teachers from Holy Cross of Agdao and Cluster 1 Division of Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for not more than 3 years; (2) secondary school teacher; and (3) teaching TLE subject. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was

purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to the aims of the research, impart authentic knowledge and truth, and prevent errors. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was explicitly conducted among elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that interests the researcher is the challenges teachers face in using interactive media instruction in the classroom to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request

voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating. Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members if they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no

conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they have to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions, and additionally, any type of communication in relation to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the results of the study. Transparency. The results of the study were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and would be placed on CDs or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the necessary qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and the researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its

completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully in the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do

so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher are properly secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are true to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. Findings of the study were presented through research questions – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools

Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 and the research instrument, explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, jotted down notes, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all qualitative analysis forms; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Triangulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique to analyze the results of the same study using different

data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which factors influence the information received; these factors are then changed to see if the findings were the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. It was very important because the research study's results and findings would depend on how the researcher conducted it. The trustworthiness of a research study was important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. Credibility measured how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attaining worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) stated that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is "how we ensure rigor in the research pro-

cess and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability refers to how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizers to teach reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. The researcher was interested in the student's perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader can generalize the study based on his context and address the core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of the research participants' statements to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation was thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research

process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings were consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue of “how a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques.

2.10. Analytical Framework—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted in accordance with key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher would become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and note them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., inter-

views, documents, observations), Identifying a thematic framework: The second stage occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues at this stage. The researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying data portions or sections corresponding to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotate them in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the research questions and requirements of this study. The participants disclosed their experiences as newly hired TLE teachers in their respective stations

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

during the school year 2022-2023. The newly hired TLE teachers’ experiences were also discussed regarding how they perform their functions in their respective schools.

3.1. *Experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark into the actual teaching profession*—As new in the teaching job, it elicits a mixture of feelings. Being new in the trade, teaching for the first time brings excitement for the first few days, and then these experiences progress into surprises, perhaps mostly unpleasant due to some met or unmet expectations. According to Murshidi, Konting, Elias, and Fooi (2006), “when beginning teachers enter the teaching force, they often encounter the reality shock as they confront the complexity of the teaching task. The reality of the actual teaching situation sometimes differs so much from what the beginners were expecting”. Most of these experiences could stem from the classroom full of students with different personalities and different backgrounds. Aside from the classroom where teachers stay at least 50 percent of the time (Keller, Frenze, Goetz, Pekrun, Hens-

ley, 2014), teachers’ experiences could also emanate from other interactions, e.g., with the administration, colleagues, students’ parents or other groups outside the school perimeters.

3.1.1. *Experienced Reality Shock*—Veenman first popularized the term “reality shock” to identify the experiences of newly hired teachers. Veenman (1984) summarized research conducted in the sixties, seventies, and early eighties and coined the term “reality shock.” He defined the term as “the collapse of the missionary ideals formed during teacher training due to the confrontation with the harsh and rude reality of everyday classroom life” . Chubbuck et al. (2001), suggest that new teachers experience “reality shock” when transitioning from a student identity to a teacher identity. According to Chubbuck et al. (2001), “Reality shock is the “collapse of ideals formed prior to teaching as one experiences everyday classroom life”. As-

sociated with “reality shock” is the potential for a feeling of alienation and a lack of school and systematic support that affects their efficiency in teaching (Richards et al., 2013). Beginning teachers must learn to manage the school systems and reach the differing performance expectations from various stakeholders such as students, administrators, colleagues, and parents (Richards et al., 2013). Hobson and Ashby (2012), use reality aftershock to explain the phenomenon that occurs when new teachers are put into teaching positions but no longer have the support they received from cooperating teachers during their student teaching experiences. Similar to the concept of reality aftershock or reality shock is the connection to “culture shock.” Jenkins, Smith, and Maxwell (2009) warn educators of the personal and professional isolation new teachers report feeling, which can cause a loss of personal and social identity. As new teachers try to navigate the demands of planning engaging lessons, implementing classroom management techniques, and learning about the climate, they experience “culture shock.” Jenkins et al. (2009) refer to “culture shock” as, “a teacher’s cultural capital is insufficient to deal with the cultural milieu of a classroom or school” (p. 64).

3.1.2. Overwhelmed Experiences—Newly hired teachers were overwhelmed by the challenge of transitioning to school. Many elements contributed to the “feeling of flailing” that teachers described as changing methods of delivery, uncertainty about the duration of the home learning, unclear expectations for instruction, Logistical complications of acquiring and distributing learning resources to students amidst a highly contagious pandemic. There is a need to utilize previously unused technologies and pressure from overwhelmed parents and families (Canonizado, 2020). First and second-year teachers are routinely overwhelmed (Whitcomb et al., 2008). Even when equipped with excellent teacher education, novice teachers must

learn and develop pedagogical skills, content knowledge, and workplace culture familiarity on their feet while assuming responsibility for dozens of children. Several participants articulated that they had just begun to feel comfortable, to “get in my groove,” as one teacher put it, when the pandemic hit. They had worked through early classroom management failures, built cooperative relationships with other school personnel and students. Three of the participants identified how much they were looking forward to seeing end-of-year test scores as evidence of the growth they felt they and their students had achieved. The experience of transitioning from their now more comfortable classrooms to online teaching was unsettling. Newly hired teachers were not only trying to develop their professional response to the transition but also trying to help their children transition to home learning. Other participants also acknowledged the added burden of parenting school-age children for teachers navigating the transition. However, they were not in that situation, commenting on how much more difficult this was for their colleagues. Teachers were not alone in finding the work/life balance demands of working from home while supporting their children’s learning at home. This has been a widely reported phenomenon for working parents during the pandemic (Ferdig, Baumgartner, Hartshorne, Kaplan-Rakowski, and Mouza, 2020). The added burden was significant for those few new teachers in our study who were parenting and beginning their careers as teachers.

3.1.3. Experienced Teaching through workshops—Workshop teaching and learning is the primary approach in technology and livelihood education in secondary schools in the country. Lucas, Cooper, Ward, and Cave (2009) mentioned that the students could also develop the highest sense of subject-related career opportunities from a career development perspective in a workshop set-up, which may

result from completing a degree in their field. Canter (2000) identifies the role of a workplace in helping them to grow their skills for being employed, while Calway and Murphy (2002) suggested a greater level of success among the students in both securing their employment on graduation and, compared to non-placement students, progress in their careers. Piquart et al. (2003) also suggested that increased knowledge and understanding of the industry helps to facilitate the progress from education to employment. Industry work also helps the students develop the skills needed in the industry, such as interpersonal communication and team-working, and appreciate the realities of an organization's work. Importantly, the opportunity to learn is given to able to practice and test their abilities. Students with the expertise also learn to self-assess their skills and have confidence in their ability to be able to perform the task that they are expected to accomplish in the future. In other words, they improve their self-efficacy for tasks they can expect to accomplish in the world of work.

3.1.4. Experienced Teaching Practical Knowledge—Technology and livelihood education strongly integrate the theoretical content learned at school into practical knowledge applied at home (Beinert et al., 2021) and to other school subjects, for example, mathematics (Granberg et al., 2017). The learning tasks in technology and livelihood education lessons are unique since they are rooted in student's everyday experiences and often include practical learning activities (such as food preparation and others). Therefore, the cognitive challenges that students experience in technology and livelihood education lessons are similar to those in everyday situations (Palojoki, 2003), where the decision-making process is strongly influenced by social and cultural contexts (Lave, 1988). It might be that the problem embedded in the learning task is ill-structured; it can also change

during the problem-solving process, or it can be abandoned in the light of new information or experiences. An additional challenge in home economics is that students eat the meal they have prepared together at the end of the lesson. The participants narrated their feelings towards their experiences as newly hired TLE teachers and the way of teaching through workshops. They will feel excitement. In concept as Rendahl (2018) stressed that this can be a game-changer. In home economics, planning a meal and considering various aspects is one thing; knowing that you will also eat it once it is ready is even more challenging. This kind of edible learning assignment makes technology and livelihood education unique compared to other subjects and raises questions that are still unknown. Our previous observations of group work assignments from TLE-home economics lessons have led us to believe that problems in home economics lessons are solved through several steps (similarly as in everyday situations), referred to as the gap-closing process (Lave, 1988). Students experience several cognitive challenges and critical moments while working on the cognitive or practical assignment; thereby, they need to discuss and think together to get closer to the solution of a task. This was supported by Sublay (2022). She shared her experiences in technology and livelihood education. Teachers who facilitate online learning serve as the object of the phenomenon in the study. TLE teachers who are teaching for the first time online are the participants. As a result, through their testimonies, the study can analyze how teachers' lived experiences can be investigated. Figure 3 shows the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the actual teaching profession and the emergence of the four themes: Experienced reality shock, overwhelmed experiences, experienced teaching through workshops, and experienced teaching practical knowledge.

Fig. 3. The Emerging Themes On The Experiences Of The Newly Hired TLE Teachers As They Embark Into The Actual Teaching Profession

3.2. *Coping mechanisms for success of the newly hired TLE teachers*—In constructivist studies, “teacher learning” or “learning to teach” was described as a “process of organizing and reorganizing, structuring and restructuring a teacher’s understanding of practice” (Uhlenbeck et al., 2002, p. 248). Accordingly, it can be said that the teachers, are the learners actively constructing knowledge by interpreting events using their existing knowledge, beliefs and experiences. That is why changing their beliefs enable teachers to learn new instructional practices. Existing knowledge and belief of novice teacher is mostly built during their pre-service education years. Similarly, their further understanding and beliefs was shaped by the first experiences during their induction years. It was meaningless to perceive the duties of “preparing teachers” and “developing teachers” as separate roles of different units because preparing teachers for today’s diverse classrooms is a challenging task that teacher educators should not tackle alone (Roasen, 2003) and it was neither only the personal duty of teachers themselves. Hence, Stanulis, Fallon, and Pearson (2002) proposed that university educators should become more involved in supporting new teacher learning be-

cause teacher educators stand in such a unique position that they are to understand and tolerate the needs of beginning teachers; to learn about ways former students develop as teachers; and to connect university coursework with real life experiences.

3.2.1. *Attending Mentoring and Coaching*—Mentoring and coaching programs proven to capacitate newly hired teachers in the early years in the field. Moving from student teacher to newly qualified teacher was an exciting transition, but it was not covered in preparation programs in faculties because “teaching was more than standing in front of a group and telling them what you know” (Jarvis Algozzine, 2006). Many education scholars widely agreed that the induction stage of a teacher’s career was exceptionally challenging (Huling-Austin 1990, as cited in Walsdorf Lynn, 2002). Concerns like being unprepared to meet pupils’ needs, classroom management, and understanding school culture might cause problems initially. There appear two major trends from the research on new teachers’ concerns about classroom contexts and students: a “practice shock” and a “cultural mismatch”. The former, the practice shock, as the literature defines, is “novices’ tran-

sition from idealism to the reality and complexity of classroom life” (Achinstein Barret, 2004). Stanulis, Fallon, and Pearson (2002) clarified it with a novice teacher’s statement in a survey: “Lately, it is just like mass chaos. I have tried to stay positive for the whole year, but lately, I have just had this negative concept of myself. I’m like: Oh my gosh, have I chosen the right profession? It shows that even though teacher education seems successful enough in preparing students for their future profession, the classroom reality can differ greatly from the pre-service years. No matter how good their training or college preparation was, the “real” world is different and in-service teaching reality often conflicts with the self-expectations of novices and unrealistic feelings from graduate years. Many novice teachers therefore find the transition from being student teacher to novice teacher overwhelming (Jarvis Algozzine, 2006; Lindgren, 2005). Mentoring and coaching were part of the transition from training to employment and early professional development. Induction, the first year of a teacher’s career, was a crucial and potentially difficult period. It was intended to bridge training and the rest of a teacher’s career. It stands for both a monitoring and a support program. However, induction means different in different countries. As Holmes (2006) defined, induction, in England, was “a time in which novices will be working as a teacher, with all the attendant roles and responsibilities, while also demonstrating that they can achieve certain standards that have been set for new teachers.” For instance, if one wants to teach in a maintained school or non-maintained particular school in England, he/she needs to complete his/her induction period successfully, which is “crucial and should not be underplayed” (p. 49). They cannot continue their career in the state sector unless they meet all the Induction Standards and the Standards for the Award of Qualified Teacher Status. An increasing number of school systems were recognizing

the value of teacher mentoring and coaching programs in improving the performance of new teachers. Assisting novice teachers in a supportive environment to bridge the gap between the theory in mind and the life practice in the first year when they enter the workplace was crucial. Some designated that the first year of teaching was an inevitable “embattled year” requiring novices to assume “survival mode.” Different educators described the first year of teaching as a “sink or swim scenario,” as a “harsh and rude reality of everyday teaching,” or simply as “reality shock,” almost all of which implies that new teachers come with “an unrealistic and falsifiable concept of teaching” (Lundeen, 2004).

3.2.2. *Managing Time Well*—Time management helps them to accomplish things on time. This lets them to attend school duties, do household chores, and regain energy through rest. Establishing routines through habits and practices in a set schedule helps them to utilize time efficiently. Also, taking advantage of tools and technology to be used in performing works like submission of outputs, computation of scores, checking of written works and delivery of instruction provides comfort and convenience (Raines, 2011). Effective time management increases an individual’s confidence and makes him self-assured. Fleming (2011) said that individuals who can accomplish tasks within the stipulated time frame can make their life improved and balance not only in their organization as well as amongst their peers and family. Consequently, a teacher who can manage his time well implies a well-managed classroom. Hence, he can provide an environment in which teaching and learning can flourish smoothly, resulting to positive academic achievement of the students. Moreover, the teacher can keep up with the educational needs of every student, manage urgent situations immediately and avoid falling behind when unexpected situations arise. Time management behavior was characterizing as worthwhile thing that requires to be man-

aged efficiently and acts as a key indicator of managerial economical edge (Rutte Roe, 2007). Management of time describes those behaviors that aim at accomplishing an operative time usage in acting on definite life orienting actions (Claessens, 2007). Many professions gave high demands on individuals' time. Britton and Glynn (1989) inferred them as rationally productive individuals; usually possess some extra things that are necessary to perform the tasks within a certain time span. Now such professions become more creative way to complete different job related activities even in the scarcity of time and other resources. The individual that gives great attention to their tasks always shows higher outcomes. Better time management will enhance the worker's productivity and enables them to work in smarter ways (Green Skinner, 2005). Likewise, Jamal (1984) studied that effective time management reduces job stress and increases the job performance of employees. Claessens (2004) acknowledged that better time management give more control of individual to his time and resultantly decreases the work anxiety and higher the job performance Felton (2009) said that time management is the process of planning and exercising conscious control of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency or productivity. Further, Contrell (2013) defines time management as a juggling act of various demands of study, social life, employment, family, and personal interests and commitments with the finiteness of time. Using time effectively gives the person a "choice" on spending/ managing activities at their own time and expediency. According to Bilbao (2009), scheduling, goal setting, prioritizing tasks, managing paperwork, and managing interruptions may be executed by the teachers to meet the demands of their job. These save their time without compromising the quality of teaching and service. Further, Forsyth (2010) suggested that keeping work life balance is one of necessitates to efficiently and

effectively manage the limited resources and available time.

3.2.3. Being Adaptable—In their 2012 tripartite model, Martin and colleagues (2012) establish that adaptability comprises three dimensions: a cognitive, a behavioral, and an emotional dimension. When newly hired teachers faced with a challenging, novel, or uncertain situation, cognitive adaptability involves thinking about the situation in different ways or changing one's thoughts about the situation or circumstance. Behavioral adaptability involves adjusting one's actions to manage a situation or circumstance change. Emotional adaptability involves adjusting one's emotions to reduce less helpful emotions (e.g., anxiety) or increase positive emotions (e.g., hope) in the face of novelty, change, or uncertainty. Adaptability among practicing teachers has been linked with positive teacher and student outcomes. For example, in a study of Australian secondary teachers, Collie and Martin (2017) showed that when teachers were more adaptable, they also reported greater well-being and organizational commitment. In addition, teacher adaptability was linked with students' numeracy achievement via the boost it provided to teachers' well-being. More recently, Collie et al. (2018) demonstrated that more adaptable teachers tended to be less disengaged at work. Loughland and Alonzo (2019) found that more adaptable teachers tend to use teaching practices in the classroom that adjust to the needs of the students. Most recently, Martin et al. (2019) found that adaptability among teacher assistants working with students with disabilities was associated with greater workplace motivation and occupational self-concept. Taken together, there is clear evidence of the importance of adaptability for thriving and effective teachers (and teacher assistants). However, non-cognitive skills are rarely a focus in pre-service education courses. We suggest there is a clear impetus to develop this capacity in pre-service teachers through educational psychol-

Fig. 4. The Emerging Themes On The Coping Mechanism For The Success Of The Newly Hired TLE Teachers

ogy courses. Figure 4 shows the experiences of coping mechanisms for the success of newly hired teachers and the emergence of the three themes: experienced reality shock, attending mentoring and coaching, managing time well, and being adaptable.

3.3. *Educational management insights are drawn from the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers*—Learning from the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they embark on the Teaching Profession. The transition between training and the first teaching job can be challenging, especially as there was an end to missionary ideals of teacher training and the harsh and rude reality of everyday classroom life (Menon, 2011). Actual teaching comes with integrating a multifaceted reality that forces itself persistently upon the new teacher, becoming a continual practice. According to various studies on the above subject, the main areas that pose challenges and problems to new teachers include classroom discipline, dealing with individual differences, motivating learners, relationships with parents, and organizing class work. Other areas include inadequate teaching resources, and dealing with the individual problems of certain students (Whitaker, 2003). Realizations in the detailed discussion with novice

teachers were the takeaways from their experiences and coping mechanisms in teaching in the new normal classroom.

3.3.1. *Adjusting to the School Setting*—The result of this study was in consonant with Menon (2011) that newly hired teachers have difficulties adjusting to the rules, regulations, and organizational practices at the school unit. From the studies carried out on problems that novice teachers face, it was evident that teachers were not adequately instructed about the school’s rules, regulations, and organizational practices. The lack of information on such matters points to the issues in the teacher preparation programs and the lack of effective induction practices. Adjusting to the system can be a challenge for most new teachers since there is a lack of information on schools about their organization and classrooms. New teachers must learn about routine job activities such as planning, organizing events and excursions, and student management. New teachers have mini-

mal information on the functioning of schools, which hampers the delivery of services. Usually, these new teachers start their duties in new regions and environments. Unlike other professions, teaching requires the teacher to start working immediately. New employees undergo thorough training in other professions before being assigned substantial duties in the organization (Menon, 2011). However, it was a different case for teachers as new teachers were assigned major tasks similar to those of experienced teachers without support. This was a significant challenge for new teachers as adapting to new organizational settings with inadequate support may be frustrating. This challenge also affected exceptional education teachers as this section involves several protocols, unlike the general education teachers. In special education, the support and training of beginning teachers is required. Special education teachers reported a lack of information on the system about policies, paperwork, procedures, guidelines, and expectations related to their areas of expertise. Emotional support is also necessary for new teachers, especially from experienced teachers and other people in the same organization (Whitaker, 2003). Below are some of the insights from the newly hired TLE teachers:

3.3.2. Building Professional Learning Group—Your relationships with others will keep you strong, and they will fuel your energy to persist through challenges. Build strong relationships with your colleagues, administrators, students, and parents. If they are shy, now is the time to pick up some strategies to connect with others. Ask questions, knock on doors, and invite people into their classroom. The community is a buoy when times get hard. Grant (2006) and Levine (2011) believe teachers develop and evolve into Teacher Professional Communities; these communities exist by having norms, routines, and shared vision. Teacher communities evolve naturally and are useful in understanding positive and negative student and staff outcomes

(Levine, 2011). Teacher's professional communities exist in educational settings and have a positive impact depending on the culture within the learning community. They play an intricate role in professional development. Organizational goals and vision provide the foundation necessary for professional growth to occur. Gallucci, Van Lare, Yoon, and Boatright (2010) believe professional learning must be coordinated across people, settings, and events. Teacher performance and student outcomes should be the shared responsibility by educators (Louis, Marks, Kruse, 1996). A study analyzed data collected through the National Center for Educational Statistics (NCES, 2011). It determined that schools organized with a strong commitment strategy have better success in achieving their goals—increased teacher participation in content-related professional development and greater stability in teaching staff results in increased learning outcomes. Barrier, Anson, Ording, and Evelyn (2002) found that all initiatives should be tailored to the organization's context. Employees should be engaged in defining initiatives, and high leadership commitment must be maintained for adult learning. Professional learning communities' work begins with guiding principles set through norm development (Dumay, 2009; Thoonen et al., 2011; Timperley Alton-Lee, 2008). Norms guide team members in working collaboratively by clarifying expectations on how individuals will collectively work together to achieve shared goals (DuFour, 2010). Team norms provide the structure, approach, and culture for "doing business." Levine (2011) promotes norms that include collaboration, shared objectives, respect for experienced teachers, and promotion of morale. Dumay (2009) adds to the research by showing that a shared norm of innovation appears impactful in schools with low socioeconomic composition. Below are some of the insights from the newly hired TLE teachers:

3.3.3. *Going with Positive Workmates*— Some veteran teachers are sad and cynical, and there are others who are wise and hopeful. Suppose you find yourself amongst the cynical; leave and stay far from that negativity. It would be best if you had mentors who could share their wisdom and expertise and remind you at the end of October that things will get easier. If you cannot find any in your school, look in other schools in your district. They were there, and many will happily mentor you. Instructional coaching and mentoring were tools for professional growth and learning. Zellers, Howard, and Barcic (2008) refer to the network of support for professional growth as “constellations.” Luna and Cullen (1995) refer to this structure as mosaics of supportive relationships. A qualitative (Gallucci et al., 2010) study within three urban districts implemented a coaching program where coaches learned right along- side those being coached, making the process dynamic. The design implemented specific coaching within a team of first-grade teachers interested in improving reading outcomes. It was recognized (Gallucci et al., 2010) that coaches were conduits for reform, taking information and disseminating it within their district. This coaching approach created a symbiotic relationship where learning was done between coach and teacher (Cuddapah Clayton, 2011). This relationship allowed learning to be circulated to and with others. Coaches also allowed teachers to participate in observations of other professionals. One professional development model integrated coaching within the context of teacher preparation. Castle, Fox, and Souder (2006) compared Professional Development Schools (PDS) with non-professional development schools. Their study analyzed the impact of training teachers before their employment and providing continuous support once employed. Castle et al. (2006) used this program provided by George Mason University as the basis for their belief that training is vital since inexperienced teachers, those with less than 3 years’ experience, produced smaller student learning gains than experienced teachers. The design of the PDS program was to build connectivity between theory and practice, focusing on one’s performance and then shifting to a student-centered focus. This approach found PDS students more competent in instruction, management, and assessment, all qualities necessary for an effective start as an educator. Early training for emerging educators also includes coaching and mentoring while learning the profession. This process was known as the induction into the profession. A study done by Cuddapah and Clayton (2011) with newly hired K-12 teachers evaluated the effectiveness of a curricular framework based on adult learning within a Beginning Teacher Program (BTP). Surfacing in their study was the importance of interactivity leading to collaborative talk. Similar to the development of a Professional Learning Community, Cuddapah and Clayton (2011) distinguished that this peer mentored approach allowed for critical dialogue; however, some problematic assumptions were left unchallenged. Leaving problematic assumptions unchallenged can cause environments where institutional values and norms are left, and teacher effects are detrimental. Coaches and mentors are change agents, leading people to look at the organization as a whole (Zheng et al., 2009). These change agents should possess strong and practical communication skills, motivate and provide constructive feedback, encourage staff participation in setting goals and developing plans, challenge people, and strengthen teamwork (Barrier et al., 2002). Day and Bakioglu (1996) identify mentors as within one of four stages: initiation, development, autonomy, and disenchantment. Each stage provides a different perspective necessary to those being mentored but also allows the mentor to be pushed, depending on their stage. They contend that the rapid rate of change can create incompetence among those in the profession. This reciprocal learning

can provide a mutual growth opportunity for the mentor and mentee. Below are some of the insights from the newly hired TLE teachers:

3.3.4. Observing Other Teachers—Ideally, observe the influential teachers in your school or other schools. Even if they do not teach the same thing you do, they will learn a great deal. Pick one thing to pay attention to so they do not get overwhelmed. For example, pay attention to routines and procedures, the lesson pacing, how questions were asked, or the different ways students were engaged. Ask your administrators for a release day so that you can do this. If they say no, then at the very least, take ten minutes a few times a month to poke your head into another teacher’s classroom during your prep period. They learn so much from observing their colleagues (Gore, 2013). Observing other teachers was a key part of development; it improved teachers’ self-awareness of their skills and also made managers more effective at identifying areas for further growth. It is paradoxical that opportunities to observe teachers and classes are presented more often to those who already train teachers rather than teachers themselves. In many ways, these trainers need to observe less to aid their development than those just starting as teachers (Gore, 2013). Several studies demonstrated how the peer review

model for the observation of teaching provides faculty with development opportunities and improves teaching practice (Bell, 2001; Hendry Oliver, 2012; Sullivan et al., 2012). Hendry and Oliver (2012) write that “observing a colleague teach can both show the observing teachers how new strategies work and enhance their confidence to apply them in their teaching”, and Sullivan et al. (2012) show how the peer observation of teaching can provide “an opportunity to examine both content and delivery of individual course components so that suggestions could be made as to how these might be improved or refined.” Other benefits include first-hand collegial support and the growth of teaching-related collaboration (Pressick, Killborn te Riele, 2008). Throughout the process, peer observation can be a valuable opportunity for reflection and insight into teaching practices, mutual professional development, and quality improvement in teaching and learning (Sullivan et al., 2012). Figure 5 shows the educational management insights learned from the newly hired TLE teachers’ experiences and the emergence of the two themes: adjusting to the school setting, building a professional learning group, going with positive workmates, and observing other teachers.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the study summary, the findings summary, and the implications and future directions are presented. My study’s purpose was to solicit the experiences of newly hired TLE teachers as they enter the teaching profession. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell’s (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, participants were encouraged to present their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. Findings—The findings of the study on the experiences of the newly hired TLE teachers revealed that they experienced reality shock, were overwhelmed experience, experi-

enced teaching through workshops, and experienced teaching practical knowledge. It was revealed that the newly hired TLE teachers’ coping mechanisms for success included attending

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Learned From The Experiences Of The Newly Hired TLE Teachers

mentoring and coaching, managing their time well, and being adaptable. As to the educational management insights learned from the participants, newly hired TLE teachers felt they needed to adjust to the school setting, build a professional group, work with positive workmates, and observe other teachers.

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Based on the experiences of the newly hired TLE teachers, the interview revealed the following themes: First, experiencing reality shock to embark into the actual teaching profession was a reality shock experience in the public school. Second, I experienced being overwhelmed; aside from the primary function, which was to teach in the classroom, additional functions such as coordinators were also given. Third, experienced teaching through workshops cannot be denied that workshop activities were embedded in the learning process of teaching TLE subjects. Fourth was experienced in teaching practical knowledge. Teaching TLE subjects teaches practicality in life, from basic cooking to complex ones. Knowledge and skills that were needed by the students

in the future. On the coping mechanisms for the success of the newly hired TLE teachers, one of the themes that emerged was attending mentoring and coaching. Newly hired TLE teachers were accumulating teaching skills, and mentoring and coaching were the basic ways of acquiring such knowledge. Any input from the seasoned teachers is a welcome idea for the newly hired teachers. The second theme identified by the newly hired TLE teachers' coping mechanisms for success was managing their time well. Teachers' work was unending; even at home, they still did some school work, so time management was critical. The last theme identified was to be adaptable. The ability of the newly hired teachers to adapt to the present situation was a determinant of success in being immersed in the actual teaching and learning process. It was vital to adapt immediately to a new workplace. The educational management insights learned from the experiences of the newly hired TLE teachers identified the first theme as adjusting to the public school setting, which plays an important role in surviving in the teaching profession. The second theme identified was building a professional group. As newly hired TLE teachers

embark on the actual teaching, it was essential to have a group whom they could lean on and consult in times of difficulty in the teaching and learning processes. The third theme was to go with positive workmates. With all the negativity surrounding us, and in the teaching profession, being with people with a positive outlook on life was essential. Spend time with them during their leisure time to renew their individual energy. The fourth theme the newly hired TLE teachers identified was observing other teachers. By observing the good practices of master teachers and other experts, they would learn strategies to help the classroom's teaching and learning processes.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, some important actions need to be taken and made available to newly hired teachers in technology and livelihood education subjects and across learning areas. This

study may provide an avenue to enlighten the school heads to continue supporting the quest of the newly hired teachers to be capacitated immediately. The school heads may help the newly hired teachers practically and systematically with mentoring and coaching. The newly hired teachers may continue to contact their colleagues from other schools for possible benchmarking. Despite the limited technology resources available to capacitate the newly hired teachers, they may keep encouraging all possible partners for possible partnerships in terms of knowledge acquisition. Teachers, learners, and their parents should consider making possible contributions to keeping the newly hired teachers on their side whenever help is needed. For future researchers, similar studies may be conducted in other regions or divisions. The researchers may consider other aspects of the newly hired TLE teachers' experiences.

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